

Developing and harmonising energy and digital transition narratives for future raw materials demand and supply projections

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ABSTRACT

The European Union's twin transition combines energy and digital transformations to mitigate climate change while advancing digitalisation, increasing demand for raw materials (RMs) [1–2]. Given the uncertainties surrounding this transition, scenarios are used to structure assumptions on demand, supply risks, and other factors, thereby supporting preparedness and strategic decision-making [3]. Scenarios describe internally consistent futures based on qualitative and/or quantitative assumptions [3–4], while narratives (or storylines) provide qualitative context through socio-economic, technological, and institutional conditions [5]. Existing studies project energy technologies and associated mineral demand for 2030 and 2050 [6–9] and assess supply chains under different scenarios [10]. However, these approaches often lack harmonised narratives and overlook missing drivers for the twin transition, which may hinder defossilisation and complicate resource planning in a fragmented world. Therefore, this work aims to develop and harmonise narratives to inform future RM demand, supply, and environmental impacts for the twin transition in 2030, 2050, and 2070. This presentation introduces both the process used to develop these harmonised narratives and the resulting storylines, supporting EU policy and industry decision-making. Energy transition narratives were developed through a stepwise, consensus-based process involving domain experts to identify key driving forces. Anchor scenarios—SSP1 VLLO, SSP2 Medium, SSP2 Low, and SSP2 Low with geopolitical tensions—were selected from the ScenarioMIP framework under CMIP7, based on Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) [11–12]. Synergies and interdependencies among the driving forces of the energy transition were analysed using causal loop diagrams (CLDs). Digital transition narratives were built on anchor scenarios by incorporating driving forces such as greenhouse gas footprint of hardware, software and digital services, usage patterns, regulation, and maintenance. A master CLD was developed to capture system-wide feedbacks and integrate often overlooked aspects of both transitions, including supply constraints, environmental impacts, circular economy strategies, technological developments, market shifts, geopolitical constraints, and competition for critical RMs. This process resulted in storylines as the main outcome, while their further development with qualitative and quantitative outputs is left for future work.

Keywords: Twin transition; Narratives; Critical Raw Materials, Shared Socioeconomic Pathways.

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